

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

STEM AND ROBOTICS: COMBINING EDUCATION WITH MANUFACTURING USING THE EXAMPLE OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF CNC MACHINES

**Dosymov Y.,
Kazikhanov K.,
Kelesbayev K.,
Ramankulov Sh.**

Khoja Akhmet Yassawi International Kazakh-Turkish University, Kazakhstan.

Abstract

The purpose of this study is to develop students' STEM competencies necessary for the field of production organization using the Arduino platform. It also provides for training students in such skills as automation, production process management, mastering new technologies and working in a production environment. In the course of the study, scientific papers and statistical data from various sources were analyzed, and the meta-analysis method was used. Using the Arduino platform, students develop STEM competencies and acquire the necessary skills in the field of production organization. Through the Arduino platform, students were able to learn programming languages, develop creative thinking, and improve their skills in the field of automation. This highlighted the importance of the widespread use of the Arduino platform in the education system.

Keywords: STEM education, manufacturing industry, Arduino platform, model development, education-science-production.

Introduction

STEM competence is the ability to acquire knowledge and skills related to the fields of Science (Science), Technology (Technology), Engineering (Engineering) and Mathematics (Mathematics). This competence contributes to the development of students' analytical thinking, critical thinking, creative abilities and problem-solving skills. Improving the competence of STEM learning is an important basis for the development of individual scientific literacy and international economic competitiveness of students [1]. STEM competencies are the ability to apply engineering and technology in the development of Science, Natural Science for the study of Science, Mathematics for solving practical problems, practice and projects [2]. Stem-PBL helps in the development of STEM competence. At the same time, the 21st century determined the development of skills [3]. STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) competence Awakens students' interest in technical sciences. In order to develop the STEM competence of students, he proposed to introduce a mobile robot into education. The capabilities of the robot allow you to measure physical variables, convert quantities, analyze the operation of sensors and actuators, and use control interfaces. This, in turn, showed that students contribute to the development of STEM competencies [4]. Improving STEM competencies, in particular, problem-solving skills, system skills, technology and engineering skills, time, resources and knowledge management skills will affect students in the field of production Organization [5]. The necessary STEM competencies in preparing students for the field of organization of production are engineering and technological skills. In the field of production organization, the Arduino platform is considered as an effective tool. The Arduino platform will be able to provide students with an understanding of the basic principles of the production industry. That is why the use of the Arduino

platform is a tool of great importance both in preparing students for the industrial field and in the educational field. The problem of improving the educational process of students in the scientific, technical and natural science fields is one of the most relevant aspects of modern pedagogical research. Considered the development of scientific and technical thinking of students in teaching effective programming based on the use of the Arduino platform. As a result, it convincingly proves that students have achieved a high level of development of programming skills when using the Arduino platform [6]. The use of the Arduino platform provides a great opportunity for students to develop STEM competencies. Through this platform, students learn the basics of electronics, programming skills and apply them to solving specific tasks. Arduino projects enhance students' creative thinking, problem-solving abilities, and deepen their scientific and mathematical understanding. This study aims to use the Arduino platform to answer the following research questions: - What is the role of the Arduino platform in preparing students for the field of production organization? - Does the Arduino platform have an impact on education? - Are there any advantages of the Arduino platform in the development of STEM competencies? Therefore, the purpose of this study is to determine the effectiveness of the Arduino platform in preparing students for the field of production organization, as well as the impact on the educational sphere.

Research method

In the course of the study, the selection of scientific papers was selected according to predetermined criteria. the search was carried out using the keywords "competence", "STEM competence", "production sphere", "Arduino platform" and the publications of the last 5 years were taken into account. To increase the statistical significance of the results, we used meta-analysis – a method of combining the results of several

scientific papers to formulate general conclusions. Modeling, design methods: the use of the Arduino platform in order to prepare students for the field of Organization of production was found to be effective in the design and development of students.

Research results and discussion

The use of the Arduino platform has a great impact on preparing students for the field of production organization. Arduino is an open source hardware and software platform. One of its main features is the ease and flexibility of use. With the Arduino platform, students have the opportunity to create different projects and solve specific tasks. We have experimentally considered the possibilities of using the Arduino platform in preparing students for the field of production organization. In the field of modern production and technologies, production, digital program management occupies an important place. Digital software control is a technology for the automated control of various machines,

including milling machines, lathes, laser cutters and 3D printers. The relationship of CNC (digital software control) technology with the Arduino platform is important because Arduino's accessibility and flexibility make it an effective tool for assembling and controlling CNC machines. It is possible to create a CNC machine through the Arduino platform, which will allow students to teach how the technology works. It also contributes to the preparation of production in the field of organization. For example, in preparing students for the field of production organization, we implemented the STEAM project using the Arduino platform by creating a CNC machine (Figure 1). The main goal of the development of this project is to teach students the basics of industrial automation, develop creative and critical thinking skills, as well as the formation of technical and engineering skills necessary to solve specific production problems.

Figure 1. CNC machine

When designing and installing electrical circuits, it is necessary to carefully monitor the voltage level. To ensure the correct operation of stepper motors, it is important to choose the right voltage level and correctly control the switches. This is necessary to ensure the safety and durability of the electrical circuit. Step two: install the software. To download code to an Arduino board, you first need to install the Arduino IDE software. You can download the Arduino software here: [ARDUINO SOFTWARE LINK](#). The installation process consists of the following steps:

- 1.choosing the right version: if you are using a PC (pc), download the version for Windows. Select the version that suits your operating system.

- 2.installation: open the downloaded file and complete the installation process. During the installation process, select the necessary parameters and follow all the instructions.

- 3.Library import: after the Arduino IDE is installed, you need to import the module's Shield library. This step is mandatory because if the library is not imported, the code will display an error stating that the required library is missing. To import the library, you need to go to the sketch menu. Sketch is a code written specifically for Arduino. You can insert the sketch you wrote into the Arduino IDE and upload it to the Arduino board. The last step is to compile the code. After downloading the code to the Arduino board, you must choose the correct Arduino board type. In this case, we chose the Arduino original/Uno type. After connecting

the Arduino board to the computer, you need to install the correct communication port (Com-port) on it. Once the executable hardware and Com-port are defined, you can start compiling the code. If all the steps are completed successfully and there are no errors, the Arduino board will be compiled and run. Now the circuit board can no longer be changed, as it will work ready-made.

By following these steps, we have successfully developed a CNC machine (digital software control). This project reflects the essence of STEAM education and allows students to get acquainted with modern production technologies and understand their practical application. In addition, in the process of developing a CNC machine, students develop research skills, which stimulates them to implement innovative projects in the future. Thus, an effective and promising method is to prepare students for the field of production organization using the Arduino platform and CNC technology. The results of this study have greatly contributed to the development of technical, creative, and professional skills of students in designing and controlling a CNC machine using the Arduino platform. This study increased students' readiness for the future industry, encouraged them to work with modern technologies and explore new professional areas. Our research used the Arduino circuit board to prepare students for the field of production organization. As a result, students will be able to develop their mathematical skills in research, technology, engineering and calculation of the expected result

by creating a product. This contributes to the development of STEM competencies, as students acquire the skills necessary to solve problems in real life.

Conclusion

The Arduino platform allows students to apply their theoretical knowledge in practice. Students master the basics of programming, electronics and engineering in the process of implementing specific projects. Students will learn how to collect data and analyze them using various sensors and devices in their practice. This improves their research skills and forms their scientific vision. Students, working with new technologies, adapt to the requirements of modern production. The use of the Arduino platform in the educational process allows you to comprehensively prepare students for the field of Organization of production. This approach will increase their STEM competence and allow them to acquire knowledge and skills that meet the requirements of modern production.

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